

TERMINOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF INTERNET ABBREVIATIONS IN ENGLISH

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Annotation: The Internet (or Internet) is an Internet protocol suite (TCP/IP) used by interconnected global system computer networks to communicate between networks and devices. The Internet includes many information resources and services such as interconnection, the World Wide Web of hypertext documents and applications (WWW), email, telephony and file sharing. However, “some could have multiple meanings depending on their context..

Key words: requirements, WWW (World Wide Web of hypertext documents and applications), internet, abbreviations, system, disk, type, display, input, row, storage.

Аннотация: Интернет (или Интернет) - это набор Интернет-протоколов (TCP /IP), используемый взаимосвязанными глобальными системными компьютерными сетями для связи между сетями и устройствами. Интернет включает в себя множество информационных ресурсов и услуг, таких как межсетевое взаимодействие, всемирная паутина гипертекстовых документов и приложений (WWW), электронная почта, телефония и совместное использование файлов. Однако «некоторые могут иметь несколько значений в зависимости от контекста.

Ключевые слова: требования, WWW (Всемирная паутина гипертекстовых документов и приложений), Интернет, сокращения, система, диск, тип, отображение, ввод, строка, хранилище.

Аннотация: Интернет (ёки Интернет) - бу тармоқ протоколлари тўплами (ТСП / ИП) глобал тармоқ компьютер тармоқлари томонидан тармоқлар ва қурилмалар ўртасида алоқа қилиш учун ишлатилади. Интернет ўзаро боғлиқлик, гиперматнли ҳужжатлар ва дастурларнинг бутун дунё тармоғи (WWW), электрон почта, телефония ва файлларни алмашиш каби кўплаб ахборот ресурслари ва хизматларини ўз ичига олади. Бироқ, «баъзилари ўз мазмунига қараб бир нечта маънога эга бўлиши мумкин.

Таянч сўзлар: талаблар, WWW (бутун дунё бўйлаб гиперматнли ҳужжатлар ва дастурларнинг Интернет тармоғи), интернет, қисқартмалар, тизим, диск, тип, дисплей, кириш, қатор, сақлаш.

Abbreviations come in several varieties. Both abbreviations and initial words are abbreviations formed by combining the first letter of each word in a longer noun or

phrase. Usually abbreviations and initialisms are written in all capital letters to distinguish them from ordinary words. The abbreviation is pronounced as a single word, not a series of letters. For example, NASA is an abbreviation. This means national aeronautics and space administration. Sometimes an acronym becomes so common that it becomes a simple word and people no longer think of it as an acronym. For example, the words scuba and laser appeared as acronyms (spontaneous underwater breathing apparatus and amplification of radiation with stimulated radiation, respectively). Initialisms are similar to abbreviations because they are formed using the first letter in the longer phrase of each word. The origins of the Internet began with its development, the replacement of packets, and research commissioned by the United States Department of Defense in the 1960s to allocate time to turn on computers.

The network of primary precursors, the ARPANET, initially served as the basis for interconnecting regional academic and military networks in the 1970s. Funding The National Science Foundation Network as a new backbone in the 1980s, as well as private financing of other commercial extensions, led to global participation in the development of new network technologies and the merging of many industries. In the early 1990s, the interconnection of commercial networks and enterprises began the transition to the modern Internet, and created a steady exponential growth as institutional generations, with personal and mobile computers connected to the network. Although widely used by the Internet, the academy introduced commercialization of its services and technologies in almost every aspect of modern life in the 1980s.

Many traditional means of communication, including telephony, radio, television, paper mail, and newspapers, are being reshaped, rescheduled, or even bypassed by the Internet, and new services such as email are being born. Internet telephony, Internet television, online music, digital newspapers and video streaming websites. Newspapers, books and other print publications adapt to website technology or reformed blogging, web channels and online news collectors. It has activated and accelerated new forms of personal interaction over the Internet, instant messaging, Internet forums and social networking services. Online shopping has grown dramatically for large retailers, small businesses and entrepreneurs, as these firms sell their “bricks and mortar” to a larger market or even sell goods and services completely online. From business to business and financial services Internet impact supply chains across all sectors.

There is no single centralized management of the Internet in either the technology program or the access and use policy; each component network sets its own policy. The redundant definitions of both bases are managed by the maintenance organization in the Internet Protocol Address (IP Address) field and the Domain

Name System (DNS).

The Internet, as a virtual space, is in many ways similar to a real space, and to find something on the network, you need to know the location of that thing. Say: nonsense, no address needed. We enter a word or phrase related to what interests us into Yandex or Google and select the desired sites from the list of search results.

Microcontroller (English Micro Controller Unit, MCU) is a chip designed to control electronic devices. A simple microcontroller combines the functions of a processor and external devices on a single chip, including RAM and or ROM. Basically, it is a single-chip computer capable of performing relatively simple tasks. It differs from a microprocessor in integrated input-output devices, timers, and other peripherals. People on the planet speak different languages, do not know a foreign language, it is very difficult to read the texts in it. What are the ways to overcome the language barrier in site construction? For some time now, various electronic translators have been appearing and translating from one language to another.

It is no coincidence that we call the Internet, even if it is virtual, not a part of the living space, but a place with its own laws and traditions. The World Wide Web (the main part of the Internet) also has its own language, or at least jargon. It is very diverse, the number of words (phrases, concepts) is constantly increasing.

Autocode - is basically a programming language that is structurally similar to commands and processed data of a particular machine language.

Adaptive web design - is the design of web pages that ensures that the site is displayed correctly on various devices connected to the Internet and dynamically adjusts the given dimensions of the browser window. Rather, it is called a flexible layout of a website, not a design.

The purpose of impressive design - is the versatility of the site for different devices. It is not necessary to create separate versions of the site for some types of devices using sensitive web design technology to conveniently view the website from devices that fit different screen sizes and proportions (width / height).

An IT specialist - is an information technology specialist or simply a computer specialist

Account (English account - account) - a user account on a social network, forum or simply a site that provides some information about the user. Accounts are used to identify users and personalize the connection on the Internet. However, the information provided is usually not verified and may contain corrupted or imaginary personal information.

An algorithm - is a sequence of actions that leads to solving a task or achieving the desired result.

Software architecture - is the most important set of decisions on how to organize

a software system:

- linking selected elements of structure and behavior to increasingly larger systems;
- The architectural style that governs the entire organization - all the elements, their interfaces, their collaboration and communication.

Documenting the software architecture simplifies the communication process between developers, allows them to record design decisions made and inform system operating staff about them, and reuse components and project templates in others.

A computer mouse - is a coordinate device for controlling the cursor and giving various commands to a computer. Cursor control is done by moving the mouse over the surface of the table or mouse. The mouse buttons and wheel cause certain actions, for example: activating the displayed object, calling the context menu, turning web pages and electronic documents vertically.

Source text - required for additional translation information

The modulator in the modem modulates the carrier signal in the data transmission, i.e. changes its properties in accordance with the changes in the input data signal, the demodulator performs the reverse process when receiving data from the communication channel. The modem acts as a terminal equipment of the communication line. The transmission and processing of the received data is done by the so-called data generation.

Megabytes (MB, MB) - is a unit of measurement for the amount of data equal to 1,000,000 (10⁶) or 1,048,576 (2²⁰) bytes, depending on the context.

Online (English online (on line) - on line, in communication, network ", on air) - in connection mode. For example, it can show the status of the user in the forum.

In shortly say, the Internet is not just a media and a universal reference, but a means of communication. If the topic is very interesting and faithful, the visitor, the places visited, are those who are from “church” (from the English community) or a group from “Society” (English) or “community”. If you think about how many tools and methods of communication in the world, there are many and most of them are related to the Internet. So, there are different ways to communicate on the Internet: e-mail, forums, Internet magazines. If you think about it, forms of communication on the Internet create a picture and resemblance of forms of communication in real life. Thus, the form of communication by mail is old, here and on the Internet we communicate with the e-mail sent from the mailbox to the designated mailbox. True, the whole procedure using the Internet is around 5 minutes, the whole procedure takes a long time. These abbreviations may be a little more complicated for most users, but not for everyday users.

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